

Supersonic triple deck flow due to thermal disturbances

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Abstract

The fluid flow along a flat plate is excited by a thermal disturbance to develop into a triple deck structure. Essentially, the plate is either thermally insulated or its dry side (not exposed to the fluid) is maintained at fixed temperature. In the former case, the disturbance is in the form of heat flux through a finite extent. In the latter case, the disturbance is in the form of a change in the dry side temperature invoked either downstream of a point or along a finite extent. When the disturbance is small, the flow is governed, in the first approximation, by a linear problem, whose analysis is addressed.

1. Introduction

The triple deck theory has proven successful in describing fluid flow phenomena of upstream influence and flow separation. Several triggering agents of the triple deck structure has been studied, of which we are interested in thermal disturbances.

The supersonic triple deck flow past a flat plate experiencing a sudden change in surface temperature was treated by Inger [1]. Koroteev and Lipatov [2] treated the case of local change of arbitrary form. Both references presented analytical treatment of the linear problem with comparison to the numerical solution of the nonlinear problem.

The current work addresses two other cases of thermal disturbance. The case of an insulated plate that allows local heat flux, and the case of a conducting plate whose dry side experiences either extended or local change in temperature. In either case, the linear problem is treated analytically.

2. Lower Deck Problem

When a Blasius boundary layer flow encounters a suitably scaled disturbance, it develops into a triple deck structure of upper, middle and lower decks. We are interested in the case in which the disturbance is due to a local change in thermal conditions at the flat plate surface. The continuity, momentum, and energy equations governing the lower deck flow, in this case, are

$\frac{\partial \rho U}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \rho V}{\partial y} = 0$	(1a)
$\rho U \frac{\partial U}{\partial x} + \rho V \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} + \frac{dP}{dx} = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\mu \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} \right)$	(1b)
$\rho U \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + \rho V \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \sigma \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right)$	(1c)

where U and V are the velocity components in the x direction along the plate and y direction normal to the plate, respectively. ρ is the density, P is the pressure, T is the temperature, μ is the viscosity, k is the thermal conductivity, and σ is the reciprocal of the Prandtl number. The equations of state are

$\rho T = 1, \mu = T, k = T$	(1d,e,f)
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where (1d) is for a perfect gas, while (1e) and (1f) correspond to linear variation of μ and k with T .

The viscous/inviscid interaction law is

$\lambda P = \frac{dS}{dx}$	(1g)
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where λ is the surface temperature of the oncoming boundary layer, and S is the displacement function.

At $y = 0$, the wet side of the plate (exposed to the fluid) has the adherence conditions

$U = 0, V = 0$	(1h,i)
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and, for a thermal disturbance extending along the interval $(0, x_e)$ we have the thermal condition

$k \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \kappa \{ \epsilon (T - 1) - \theta [H(x) - H(x - x_e)] \}$	(1j)
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where $H(x)$ is the Heaviside function, and κ and ϵ are introduced to account for the following three cases of thermal conditions.

Case 1: With $\epsilon = 0$ and $\kappa = 1$, (1j) corresponds to an essentially insulated surface, which admits heat flux of rate θ when $x \in (0, x_e)$.

Case 2: With $\epsilon = 1$ and $\kappa = k_s/h$, (1j) corresponds to a conductive plate of small thickness h and thermal conductivity k_s , whose adjusted temperature of unity at the dry side (not exposed to the fluid) experiences a jump θ when $x \in (0, x_e)$.

Case 3: With $\epsilon = 1$ and $\kappa = \infty$, (1j) corresponds to the case treated in [1] and [2], in which the wet surface is essentially maintained at a temperature of unity and experiences a jump θ when $x \in (0, x_e)$. This case can be obtained from Case 2 by invoking the limit $\kappa \sim \infty$, corresponding to a plate of infinite conductivity or of diminishing thickness.

The matching conditions to the middle deck and to the oncoming boundary layer are

$y \sim \infty: U \sim y - S, T \sim 1$	(1k,l)
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$x \sim -\infty: U \sim y, T \sim 1, S \sim 0$	(1m,n,o)
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The downstream condition is

$x \sim \infty: P \sim 0$	(1p)
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All symbols given above are nondimensional and properly normalized.

3. Reformulation

Use of (1d,e,f) to eliminate ρ , μ and k , in favor of the temperature T , leads to the following problem

$\frac{\partial U}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial V}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{T} \left(U \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + V \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right)$	(2a)
$U \frac{\partial U}{\partial x} + V \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} + T \frac{dP}{dx} = T \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(T \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} \right)$	(2b)
$U \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + V \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \sigma T \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(T \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right)$	(2c)
$\lambda P = \frac{dS}{dx}$	(2d)
$U(x, 0) = 0, V(x, 0) = 0$	(2e,f)
$T(x, 0) \frac{\partial T}{\partial y}(x, 0) = \kappa \{ \epsilon [T(x, 0) - 1] - \theta [H(x) - H(x - x_e)] \}$	(2g)
$y \sim \infty: U \sim y - S, T \sim 1$	(2h,i)
$x \sim -\infty: U \sim y, T \sim 1, S \sim 0$	(2j,k,l)
$x \sim \infty: P \sim 0$	(2m)

We, as it has been the custom, present an analytical solution of the linear problem, when the thermal disturbance is small. It is worth mentioning here that the Howarth-Dorodnitsyn transformation used in [1,2] to supposedly simplify the linearized analysis is no need.

4. Linear problem

In the absence of the thermal disturbance; i.e., $\theta = 0$ the flow is non-evolving with the solution

$U = y, V = 0, P = 0, T = 1, S = 0$	
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In the presence of a small disturbance $\theta = \epsilon \vartheta$ where $\epsilon \ll 1$ and $\vartheta = \pm 1$, the flow is slightly perturbed according to

$U \sim y + \epsilon u + \dots, V = \epsilon v + \dots, T = 1 + \epsilon \theta + \dots, P = \epsilon p + \dots, S = \epsilon s + \dots$	
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Substituting in the governing equations and boundary conditions and retaining the leading terms only, we get

$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = y \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x}$	(3a)
$y \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v + \frac{dp}{dx} = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \theta \right)$	(3b)
$y \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x} = \sigma \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial y^2}$	(3c)
$\lambda p = \frac{ds}{dx}$	(3d)
$u(x, 0) = 0, v(x, 0) = 0$	(3e,f,g)
$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y}(x, 0) = \kappa \{ \epsilon \theta(x, 0) - \vartheta [H(x) - H(x - x_e)] \}$	
$y \sim \infty: u \sim -s, \theta \sim 0$	(3h,i)
$x \sim -\infty: u \sim 0, \theta \sim 0, s \sim 0$	(3j,k,l)

$x \sim \infty: p \sim 0$	(3m)
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It is noted that the problem is unaltered under the replacement of $\{\vartheta, u, v, p, \theta, s\}$ by their negatives. Therefore, only cases of $\vartheta = +1$ need to be considered. It is also noted that, for $-\infty < x < 0$, the linear parabolic equation (3c) together with conditions (3g,i,k) admits the unique solution $\theta(x, y) = 0$. Hence, there is no upstream influence, as far as the temperature field is concerned.

4.1. Fourier transformation

To handle this linear problem, we apply the Fourier transform

$\bar{F}(r, y) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-irx} F(x, y) dx$	
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where F stands for any of the flow variables. The transformed problem is

$ir\bar{u} + \frac{\partial \bar{v}}{\partial y} = y \frac{\partial \bar{\theta}}{\partial x}$	(4a)
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$iry\bar{u} + \bar{v} + ir\bar{p} = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial y} + \bar{\theta} \right)$	(4b)
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$iry\bar{\theta} = \bar{\sigma} \frac{\partial^2 \bar{\theta}}{\partial y^2}$	(4c)
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$\lambda\bar{p} = ir\bar{s}$	(4d)
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$\bar{u}(r, 0) = 0, \bar{v}(r, 0) = 0$ $\frac{\partial \bar{\theta}}{\partial y}(r, 0) = \kappa \{ \epsilon \bar{\theta}(r, 0) - \vartheta \Phi(r) \}$	(4e,f,g)
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$\bar{u}(r, \infty) = -\bar{s}, \bar{\theta}(r, \infty) = 0$	(4h,i)
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where $\Phi(r) = \phi(r)(1 - e^{-ir})$, $\phi(r) = \frac{1}{ir} + \pi\delta(r)$, and $\delta(r)$ is the delta function. Note that if $\Phi(r)$ is replaced by $\phi(r)$ the problem would correspond to an extended change in thermal conditions for $x \in (0, \infty)$. Such extended change is feasible in Cases 2 and 3. In Case 1, an extended heat flux is unfeasible, leading to thermal blowup.

Differentiating (4b) with respect to y and using (4a), we get

$iry \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial y} + \bar{\theta} \right) = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial y} + \bar{\theta} \right)$	(5a)
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whose solution is

$\frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial y} + \bar{\theta} = C(r) A_i \left((ir)^{\frac{1}{3}} y \right)$	(5b)
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where $C(r)$ is an arbitrary function of integration and $A_i(z)$ is the Airy function [$A_i(0) \cong 0.3550$, $\int_0^{\infty} A_i(z) dz = \frac{1}{3}$ and $A_i'(0) \cong -0.2588$; the prime denoting differentiation with respect to the argument z].

Differentiation of (5b) with respect to y gives

$\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial y} + \bar{\theta} \right) = (ir)^{\frac{1}{3}} C(r) A_i' \left((ir)^{\frac{1}{3}} y \right)$	(5c)
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Evaluating (5c) at $y = 0$ gives

$$\left. \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial y} + \bar{\theta} \right) \right|_{y=0} = (ir)^{\frac{1}{3}} C(r) A_i'(0) \quad (5d)$$

Evaluating (4b) at $y = 0$ gives, with the help of (4f),

$$ir\bar{p} = \left. \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial y} + \bar{\theta} \right) \right|_{y=0} \quad (6a)$$

so that, upon use of (5d)

$$\bar{p} = (ir)^{-\frac{2}{3}} C(r) A_i'(0) \quad (6b)$$

Substituting (6b) in (4d)

$$\bar{s} = \lambda (ir)^{-\frac{5}{3}} C(r) A_i'(0) \quad (7a)$$

Substituting (7a) in (4h)

$$\bar{u}(r, \infty) = -\lambda (ir)^{-\frac{5}{3}} C(r) A_i'(0) \quad (7b)$$

Integration of (5b), with the help of (4e,i), gives

$$\bar{u}(r, y) + \int_0^y \bar{\theta}(r, \eta) d\eta = C(r) \int_0^y A_i \left((ir)^{\frac{1}{3}} \eta \right) d\eta = (ir)^{-\frac{1}{3}} C(r) \int_0^{(ir)^{\frac{1}{3}} y} A_i(z) dz \quad (8a)$$

so that

$$\bar{u}(r, \infty) = (ir)^{-\frac{1}{3}} C(r) \int_0^\infty A_i(z) dz - \int_0^\infty \bar{\theta}(r, y) dy \quad (8b)$$

Substituting (5c), (6b) and (8a) in (4b) gives

$$\bar{v} = C(r) \left\{ (ir)^{\frac{1}{3}} [A_i' \left((ir)^{\frac{1}{3}} y \right) - A_i'(0)] - iry \left[(ir)^{-\frac{1}{3}} \int_0^{(ir)^{\frac{1}{3}} y} A_i(z) dz - \int_0^y \bar{\theta}(r, \eta) d\eta \right] \right\} \quad (9)$$

Substituting (8b) in (7b) and rearranging

$$C(r) = \frac{(ir)^{\frac{5}{3}} \int_0^\infty \bar{\theta}(r, y) dy}{(ir)^{\frac{4}{3} - \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}}} \int_0^\infty A_i(z) dz} \quad (10)$$

where $\alpha = \left[\frac{\lambda |A_i'(0)|}{\int_0^\infty A_i(z) dz} \right]^{\frac{3}{4}} \cong 0.8272 \lambda^{\frac{3}{4}}$.

Turning to the thermal problem, (4c) integrates to

$$\bar{\theta} = E(r) A_i \left[\left(\frac{ir}{\sigma} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} y \right] \quad (11a)$$

so that

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\theta}}{\partial y} = E(r) \left(\frac{ir}{\sigma}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} A_i' \left[\left(\frac{ir}{\sigma}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} y\right] \quad (11b)$$

Substitution of (11a,b), evaluated at $y = 0$, in (4g) and rearranging

$$E(r) = \frac{\vartheta}{A_i(0)} \Phi(r) \frac{\kappa\gamma}{(ir)^{\frac{1}{3}} + \epsilon\kappa\gamma} \quad (12)$$

where $\gamma = \frac{\sigma^{\frac{1}{3}} A_i(0)}{|A_i'(0)|}$.

Substituting (12) in (11a,b)

$$\bar{\theta} = \vartheta \Phi(r) \frac{\kappa\gamma}{(ir)^{\frac{1}{3}} + \epsilon\kappa\gamma} \frac{A_i \left[\left(\frac{ir}{\sigma}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} y\right]}{A_i(0)} \quad (13a)$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\theta}}{\partial y} = \frac{\vartheta}{\gamma} \Phi(r) \frac{\kappa\gamma (ir)^{\frac{1}{3}}}{(ir)^{\frac{1}{3}} + \epsilon\kappa\gamma} \frac{A_i' \left[\left(\frac{ir}{\sigma}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} y\right]}{|A_i'(0)|} \quad (13b)$$

At the surface $y = 0$, with $\beta = (\kappa\gamma)^3$

$$\bar{\theta}(r, 0) = \vartheta \Phi(r) \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}}}{(ir)^{\frac{1}{3}} + \epsilon\beta^{\frac{1}{3}}} \quad (14a)$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\theta}}{\partial y}(r, 0) = -\frac{\vartheta}{\gamma} \Phi(r) \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}} (ir)^{\frac{1}{3}}}{(ir)^{\frac{1}{3}} + \epsilon\beta^{\frac{1}{3}}} \quad (14b)$$

Integrating (13a)

$$\int_0^{\infty} \bar{\theta}(r, y) dy = \frac{\vartheta \sigma^{\frac{2}{3}} \lambda}{\gamma \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}}} \Phi(r) \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}} (ir)^{-\frac{1}{3}}}{(ir)^{\frac{1}{3}} + \epsilon\beta^{\frac{1}{3}}} \quad (15)$$

so that (10) gives

$$C(r) = \frac{\vartheta \sigma^{\frac{2}{3}}}{\gamma |A_i'(0)|} \Phi(r) \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}} (ir)^{\frac{4}{3}}}{[(ir)^{\frac{4}{3}} - \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}}] [(ir)^{\frac{1}{3}} + \epsilon\beta^{\frac{1}{3}}]} \quad (16)$$

Substitution (16) in (5b) evaluated at $y = 0$, and in (6b) gives

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial y}(r, 0) + \bar{\theta}(r, 0) = \vartheta \sigma^{\frac{1}{3}} \Phi(r) \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}} (ir)^{\frac{4}{3}}}{[(ir)^{\frac{4}{3}} - \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}}] [(ir)^{\frac{1}{3}} + \epsilon\beta^{\frac{1}{3}}]} \quad (17)$$

and

$$\bar{p}(r) = -\frac{\vartheta \sigma^{\frac{2}{3}}}{\gamma} \Phi(r) \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}} (ir)^{\frac{2}{3}}}{[(ir)^{\frac{4}{3}} - \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}}] [(ir)^{\frac{1}{3}} + \epsilon\beta^{\frac{1}{3}}]} \quad (18)$$

(14a), (14b), (17) and (18) correspond to Case 1 when $\epsilon = 0$, $\beta = \gamma^3$, to Case 2 when $\epsilon = 1$, $\beta = (\gamma k_s/h)^3$, and to Case 3 when $\epsilon = 1$, $\beta \sim \infty$.

4.2. Inverse Fourier transformation

The inverse transform

$$F(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{irx} \bar{F}(r, y) dr$$

is now applied to $\bar{\theta}$ of (14a), $\frac{\partial \bar{\theta}}{\partial y}$ of (14b), $\frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial y}$ of (17) and \bar{p} (18), all of which do not involve y .

In Cases 2 and 3 and formally in Case 1, we can treat the problem of sudden change through the replacement of $\Phi(r)$ by $\phi(r)$. Then, the problem of local change can be accounted for through translation and superposition.

In Case 1, (14b) reduces to

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\theta}}{\partial y}(r, 0) = -\vartheta \left[\frac{1}{ir} + \pi \delta(r) \right] \quad (19b)_1$$

which transforms to the corresponding surface condition $\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y}(x, 0) = -\vartheta H(x)$, while (14a) reduces to

$$\bar{\theta}(r, 0) = \vartheta \gamma \left[\frac{1}{ir} + \pi \delta(r) \right] (ir)^{-\frac{1}{3}} \quad (19a)_1$$

In Case 3, (14a) reduces to

$$\bar{\theta}(r, 0) = \vartheta \left[\frac{1}{ir} + \pi \delta(r) \right] \quad (19a)_3$$

which transforms to the corresponding surface condition $\theta(x, 0) = \vartheta H(x)$, while (14b) reduces to

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\theta}}{\partial y}(r, 0) = -\frac{\vartheta}{\gamma} \left[\frac{1}{ir} + \pi \delta(r) \right] (ir)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (19b)_3$$

The expressions for the inverse transform of (19a)₁, (14a), (14b), (19b)₃ are

$$\theta(x, 0) = \vartheta \gamma \frac{3x}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (ir)^{-\frac{1}{3}} e^{irx} dr \quad (20a)_1$$

$$\theta(x, 0) = \vartheta \left[\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{1}{ir} - \frac{(ir)^{-\frac{2}{3}}}{(ir)^{\frac{1}{3} + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}}}} \right\} e^{irx} dr + \frac{1}{2} \right] \quad (20a)_2$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y}(x, 0) = -\frac{\vartheta}{\gamma} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}} (ir)^{-\frac{2}{3}}}{(ir)^{\frac{1}{3} + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}}}} e^{irx} dr \quad (20b)_2$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y}(x, 0) = -\frac{\vartheta}{\gamma} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (ir)^{-\frac{2}{3}} e^{irx} dr \quad (20b)_3$$

Note that the terms involving $\delta(r)$ have been accounted for through $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \delta(r) F(r) dr = F(0)$, (20a)₁ has been reached through integration by parts, and (20b)₃ can be obtained from (20b)₂ through the limit $\beta \sim \infty$.

Similarly, the expressions for the inverse transform of (17) and (18) are

$\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(x, 0) + \theta(x, 0) = \vartheta \sigma^{\frac{1}{3}} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}} (ir)^{\frac{1}{3}}}{[(ir)^{\frac{4}{3}} - \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}}][(ir)^{\frac{1}{3}} + \epsilon \beta^{\frac{1}{3}}]} e^{irx} dr$	(20c)
$p(x) = -\frac{\vartheta \sigma^{\frac{2}{3}}}{\gamma} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}} (ir)^{-\frac{1}{3}}}{[(ir)^{\frac{4}{3}} - \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}}][(ir)^{\frac{1}{3}} + \epsilon \beta^{\frac{1}{3}}]} e^{irx} dr$	(20d)

To carry out the integrations in (20), we replace the real variable r by the complex variable ζ and perform suitable contour integrations in the complex ζ plane. The presence of fractional powers of ζ demands a branch cut that is taken to be along the positive imaginary axis.

We need to consider regions of negative and positive x , separately. The results are presented without elaboration, as the procedures are, by now, routine.

Fig.1

Fig. 2

4.2.1. Inversion on $-\infty < x < 0$

We integrate along the contour depicted in Fig. 1, to get the following.

The integral in (20c) gives $-2\pi \frac{3\beta^{\frac{1}{3}}}{4(\alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \epsilon \beta^{\frac{4}{3}})} e^{\alpha x}$, so that, with $\theta(x, 0) = 0$,

$\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(x, 0) = -\frac{3\vartheta \sigma^{\frac{1}{3}} \beta^{\frac{1}{3}}}{4(\alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \epsilon \beta^{\frac{4}{3}})} e^{\alpha x}$	(21c)
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The integral in (20d) gives $-2\pi \frac{3\beta^{\frac{1}{3}}}{4\alpha^{\frac{4}{3}}(\alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \epsilon \beta^{\frac{4}{3}})} e^{\alpha x}$, so that

$p(x) = \frac{3\vartheta \sigma^{\frac{2}{3}} \beta^{\frac{1}{3}}}{4\gamma \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}}(\alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \epsilon \beta^{\frac{4}{3}})} e^{\alpha x}$	(21d)
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which differentiates to

$\frac{dp}{dx}(x) = \frac{3\vartheta \sigma^{\frac{2}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{1}{3}} \beta^{\frac{1}{3}}}{4\gamma(\alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \epsilon \beta^{\frac{4}{3}})} e^{\alpha x}$	(21e)
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It is noted that, whereas the velocity/pressure field exhibits upstream influence, the temperature field does not. This is not surprising as, while the nonlinear eigen value problem of the former field demands a downstream condition to capture the appropriate eigen solution involving upstream propagation of information, the linear parabolic problem of the latter field strictly propagates upstream information toward downstream.

4.2.2. Inversion on $0 < x < \infty$

We integrate along the contour depicted in Fig. 2, to get the following.

(20a)₁ gives

$$\theta(x, 0) = \vartheta \gamma \frac{3\sqrt{3}x}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty r^{-\frac{1}{3}} e^{-rx} dr$$

so that, upon the substitution $r = t/x$

$\theta(x, 0) = \vartheta \gamma \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} x^{\frac{1}{3}} \int_0^\infty t^{-\frac{1}{3}} e^{-t} dt = \vartheta \gamma \frac{3\sqrt{3}\Gamma(\frac{2}{3})}{2\pi} x^{\frac{1}{3}}$	(22a) ₁
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where $\Gamma(z)$ is the Gamma function. Note that the proportionality to $x^{\frac{1}{3}}$ exhibits the aforementioned thermal blowup as x grows, in the extended change problem of Case 1.

(20a)₂ gives

$\theta(x, 0) = \vartheta \left[1 - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} \int_0^\infty \frac{r^{-\frac{2}{3}} e^{-rx}}{r^{\frac{2}{3} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{\frac{1}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}}}} dr \right]$	(22a) ₂
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so that, upon the substitution $r = \beta t^3$ in the integral

$$\theta(x, 0) = \vartheta \left[1 - \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{e^{-\beta t^3 x}}{t^2 + t + 1} dt \right]$$

Setting $x = 0^+$

$$\theta(0^+, 0) = \vartheta \left[1 - \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{t^2 + t + 1} dt \right] = 0$$

I.e., the plate temperature T is continuous at $x = 0$; having, there, the value of unity. As x increases T increases monotonically; reaching the asymptotic value $1 + \varepsilon\vartheta$ as $x \sim \infty$.

(20b)₂ gives

$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y}(x, 0) = -\frac{\vartheta \sqrt{3}}{\gamma 2\pi} \beta^{\frac{2}{3}} \int_0^\infty \frac{r^{-\frac{2}{3}} e^{-rx}}{r^{\frac{2}{3} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{\frac{1}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}}}} dr$	(22b) ₂
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so that, upon the substitution $r = \beta t^3$

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y}(x, 0) = -\vartheta \kappa \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{e^{-\beta t^3 x}}{t^2 + t + 1} dt$$

and setting $x = 0^+$

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y}(0^+, 0) = -\vartheta \kappa \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{t^2+t+1} dt = -\vartheta \kappa$$

in accordance with (3g).

(20b)₃ gives,

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y}(x, 0) = -\frac{\vartheta \sqrt{3}}{\gamma 2\pi} \int_0^\infty r^{-\frac{2}{3}} e^{-rx} dr$$

which, can be obtained from (22b)₂ through the limit $\beta \rightarrow \infty$, and which gives, upon the substitution $r = t/x$,

$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y}(x, 0) = -\frac{\vartheta \sqrt{3}}{\gamma 2\pi} x^{-\frac{1}{3}} \int_0^\infty t^{-\frac{2}{3}} e^{-t} dt = -\frac{\vartheta \sqrt{3} \Gamma(\frac{1}{3})}{\gamma 2\pi} x^{-\frac{1}{3}}$	(22b) ₃
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This reveals that the discontinuity at $x = 0$ and the approach to zero as $x \sim \infty$ are $O(x^{-\frac{1}{3}})$.

(20c) and (20d) give

$\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(x, 0) + \theta(x, 0) = \vartheta \sigma^{\frac{1}{3}} \left[\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{-\beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^2 + \epsilon \beta^{\frac{2}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} r^{\frac{1}{3}}}{(r^3 + r^{\frac{4}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \alpha^{\frac{8}{3}})(r^3 + \epsilon \beta^{\frac{2}{3}} r^{\frac{4}{3}} + \epsilon \beta^{\frac{8}{3}})} e^{-rx} dr \right]$	(22c)
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$p(x) = \frac{\vartheta \sigma^{\frac{2}{3}}}{\gamma} \left[\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\epsilon \beta^{\frac{2}{3}} r + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \epsilon \beta^{\frac{2}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} r^{-\frac{1}{3}}}{(r^3 + r^{\frac{4}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \alpha^{\frac{8}{3}})(r^3 + \epsilon \beta^{\frac{2}{3}} r^{\frac{4}{3}} + \epsilon \beta^{\frac{8}{3}})} e^{-rx} dr \right]$	(22d)
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5. Extended disturbance results

Combining the results obtained above, we have, noting that the results for Case 1 are inapplicable as such,

$\theta(x, 0) = \vartheta \gamma \frac{3\sqrt{3} \Gamma(\frac{2}{3})}{2\pi} x^{\frac{1}{3}} H(x)$	(23a) ₁
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$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y}(x, 0) = -\vartheta H(x)$	(23b) ₁
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$\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(x, 0) + \theta(x, 0) = -\vartheta \frac{\sigma^{\frac{1}{3}} \gamma}{\alpha^{\frac{1}{3}}} \left[\frac{3}{4} e^{\alpha x} H(-x) + H(x) \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\alpha^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{\frac{4}{3}}}{r^{\frac{8}{3}} + r^{\frac{4}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \alpha^{\frac{8}{3}}} e^{-rx} dr \right]$	(23c) ₁
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$p(x) = \vartheta \frac{\sigma^{\frac{2}{3}}}{\alpha} \left[\frac{3}{4} e^{\alpha x} H(-x) + H(x) \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\alpha^{\frac{7}{3}} r^{-\frac{2}{3}}}{r^{\frac{8}{3}} + r^{\frac{4}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \alpha^{\frac{8}{3}}} e^{-rx} dr \right]$	(23d) ₁
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$\theta(x, 0) = \vartheta H(x) \left[1 - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{-\frac{2}{3}} e^{-rx}}{r^{\frac{2}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{\frac{4}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{8}{3}}} dr \right]$	(23a) ₂
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$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y}(x, 0) = -\vartheta \kappa H(x) \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{-\frac{2}{3}} e^{-rx}}{r^{\frac{2}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{\frac{1}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}}} dr$	(23b) ₂
$\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(x, 0) + \theta(x, 0) = \vartheta \sigma^{\frac{1}{3}} \left[-\frac{3}{4} \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}}}{\alpha^{\frac{2}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}}} e^{\alpha x} H(-x) \right. \\ \left. + H(x) \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{-\beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^2 + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} r^{\frac{1}{3}}}{(r^{\frac{2}{3}} + r^{\frac{1}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{2}{3}} + \alpha^{\frac{1}{3}})(r^{\frac{2}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{\frac{1}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}})} e^{-rx} dr \right]$	(23c) ₂
$p(x) = \vartheta \frac{\sigma^{\frac{2}{3}}}{\gamma} \left[\frac{3}{4} \frac{\alpha^{-\frac{2}{3}} \beta^{\frac{1}{3}}}{\alpha^{\frac{2}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}}} e^{\alpha x} H(-x) + H(x) \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\beta^{\frac{2}{3}} r + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} r^{-\frac{1}{3}}}{(r^{\frac{2}{3}} + r^{\frac{1}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{2}{3}} + \alpha^{\frac{1}{3}})(r^{\frac{2}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{\frac{1}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}})} e^{-rx} dr \right]$	(23d) ₂
$\theta(x, 0) = \vartheta H(x)$	(23a) ₃
$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y}(x, 0) = -\frac{\vartheta}{\gamma} H(x) \frac{\sqrt{3} \Gamma(\frac{1}{3})}{2\pi} x^{-\frac{1}{3}}$	(23b) ₃
$\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(x, 0) + \theta(x, 0) = \vartheta \sigma^{\frac{1}{3}} \left[-\frac{3}{4} e^{\alpha x} H(-x) + H(x) \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} r^{\frac{1}{3}}}{r^{\frac{2}{3}} + r^{\frac{1}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{2}{3}} + \alpha^{\frac{1}{3}}} e^{-rx} dr \right]$	(23c) ₃
$p(x) = \vartheta \frac{\sigma^{\frac{2}{3}}}{\gamma \alpha^{\frac{2}{3}}} \left[\frac{3}{4} e^{\alpha x} H(-x) + H(x) \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\alpha^{\frac{2}{3}} r + \alpha^2 r^{-\frac{1}{3}}}{r^{\frac{2}{3}} + r^{\frac{1}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{2}{3}} + \alpha^{\frac{1}{3}}} e^{-rx} dr \right]$	(23d) ₃

5.1. Conditions at $x = 0^\pm$

In view of the results of Appendix A, we have the following.

$\theta(0^-, 0) = \theta(0^+, 0) = 0$	(24a) ₂
$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y}(0^-, 0) = 0$	(24b) ₂
$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y}(0^+, 0) = -\vartheta \kappa$	(24b) ₂
$\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(0^-, 0) = \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(0^+, 0) = -\vartheta \frac{3}{4} \sigma^{\frac{1}{3}} \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}}}{\alpha^{\frac{2}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}}}$	(24c) ₂
$p(0^-) = p(0^+) = \vartheta \frac{3}{4} \frac{\sigma^{\frac{2}{3}}}{\gamma \alpha^{\frac{2}{3}}} \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}}}{\alpha^{\frac{2}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}}}$	(24d) ₂
$\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(0^-, 0) = -\vartheta \frac{3}{4} \sigma^{\frac{1}{3}}$	(24c) ₃
$\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(0^+, 0) = \vartheta \left(\frac{1}{4} \sigma^{\frac{1}{3}} - 1 \right)$	(24c) ₃
$p(0^-) = p(0^+) = \vartheta \frac{3}{4} \frac{\sigma^{\frac{2}{3}}}{\gamma \alpha^{\frac{2}{3}}}$	(24d) ₃

6. Local disturbance results

By translation and superposition, the results for a local change, are

$\theta(x, 0) = \vartheta \gamma \frac{3\sqrt{3}\Gamma(\frac{2}{3})}{2\pi} [H(x)x^{\frac{1}{3}} - H(x-x_e)(x-x_e)^{\frac{1}{3}}]$	(25a) ₁
$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y}(x, 0) = -\vartheta [H(x) - H(x-x_e)]$	(25b) ₁
$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(x, 0) + \theta(x, 0) &= \frac{\vartheta \sigma^{\frac{1}{3}} \gamma}{\alpha^{\frac{1}{3}}} \left\{ -\frac{3}{4} [H(-x)e^{\alpha x} - H(x_e - x)e^{\alpha(x-x_e)}] \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\alpha^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{\frac{4}{3}}}{r^{\frac{8}{3} + r^{\frac{4}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{1}{3}} + \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}}}} [H(x)e^{-rx} - H(x-x_e)e^{-r(x-x_e)}] dr \right\} \end{aligned}$	(25c) ₁
$\begin{aligned} p(x) &= \frac{\vartheta \sigma^{\frac{2}{3}}}{\alpha} \left\{ \frac{3}{4} [H(-x)e^{\alpha x} - H(x_e - x)e^{\alpha(x-x_e)}] \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\alpha^{\frac{7}{3}} r^{\frac{2}{3}}}{r^{\frac{8}{3} + r^{\frac{4}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{1}{3}} + \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}}}} [H(x)e^{-rx} - H(x-x_e)e^{-r(x-x_e)}] dr \right\} \end{aligned}$	(25d) ₁
$\theta(x, 0) = \vartheta \left\{ H(x) - H(x-x_e) - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{\frac{2}{3}}}{\frac{2}{r^{\frac{8}{3} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{\frac{4}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{4}{3}}}} [H(x)e^{-rx} - H(x-x_e)e^{-r(x-x_e)}] dr \right\}$	(25a) ₂
$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y}(x, 0) = -\frac{\vartheta}{\gamma} \left\{ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\beta^{\frac{2}{3}} r^{\frac{2}{3}}}{\frac{2}{r^{\frac{8}{3} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{\frac{4}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{4}{3}}}} [H(x)e^{-rx} - H(x-x_e)e^{-r(x-x_e)}] dr \right\}$	(25b) ₂
$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(x, 0) + \theta(x, 0) &= \vartheta \sigma^{\frac{1}{3}} \left\{ -\frac{3}{4} \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}}}{\alpha^{\frac{1}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}}} [H(-x)e^{\alpha x} - H(x_e - x)e^{\alpha(x-x_e)}] \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{-\beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^2 + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} r^{\frac{1}{3}}}{(\frac{8}{r^{\frac{8}{3} + r^{\frac{4}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{1}{3}} + \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}}}) (\frac{2}{r^{\frac{8}{3} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{\frac{4}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{4}{3}}})} [H(x)e^{-rx} - H(x-x_e)e^{-r(x-x_e)}] dr \right\} \end{aligned}$	(25c) ₂
$\begin{aligned} p(x) &= \frac{\vartheta \sigma^{\frac{2}{3}}}{\gamma} \left\{ \frac{3}{4} \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}}}{\alpha^{\frac{1}{3}} (\alpha^{\frac{1}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}})} [H(-x)e^{\alpha x} - H(x_e - x)e^{\alpha(x-x_e)}] \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\beta^{\frac{2}{3}} r + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} r^{\frac{1}{3}}}{(\frac{8}{r^{\frac{8}{3} + r^{\frac{4}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{1}{3}} + \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}}}) (\frac{2}{r^{\frac{8}{3} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{\frac{4}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{4}{3}}})} [H(x)e^{-rx} - H(x-x_e)e^{-r(x-x_e)}] dr \right\} \end{aligned}$	(25d) ₂
$\theta(x, 0) = \vartheta [H(x) - H(x-x_e)]$	(25a) ₃
$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y}(x, 0) = -\frac{\vartheta}{\gamma} \frac{\sqrt{3}\Gamma(\frac{1}{3})}{2\pi} [H(x)x^{-\frac{1}{3}} - H(x-x_e)(x-x_e)^{-\frac{1}{3}}]$	(25b) ₃
$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(x, 0) + \theta(x, 0) &= \vartheta \sigma^{\frac{1}{3}} \left\{ -\frac{3}{4} [H(-x)e^{\alpha x} - H(x_e - x)e^{\alpha(x-x_e)}] \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} r^{\frac{1}{3}}}{r^{\frac{8}{3} + r^{\frac{4}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{1}{3}} + \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}}}} [H(x)e^{-rx} - H(x-x_e)e^{-r(x-x_e)}] dr \right\} \end{aligned}$	(25c) ₃
$p(x) = \vartheta \frac{\sigma^{\frac{2}{3}}}{\gamma \alpha^{\frac{1}{3}}} \left\{ \frac{3}{4} [H(-x)e^{\alpha x} - H(x_e - x)e^{\alpha(x-x_e)}] \right\}$	(25d) ₃

$$+ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\alpha^{\frac{2}{3}} r + \alpha^{\frac{6}{3}} r^{-\frac{1}{3}}}{r^{\frac{8}{3} + r^{\frac{4}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \alpha^{\frac{8}{3}}} [H(x)e^{-rx} - H(x-x_e)e^{-r(x-x_e)}] dr \}$$

Note that, in (24a)₁, $x^{\frac{1}{3}} - (x-x_e)^{\frac{1}{3}} \sim \frac{1}{3} x_e x^{-\frac{2}{3}}$ as $x \sim \infty$ so that $\theta(x, 0) \sim \vartheta \gamma \frac{\sqrt{3}\Gamma(\frac{2}{3})}{2\pi} x_e x^{-\frac{2}{3}}$, vanishing as $x \sim \infty$.

6.1 Conditions at $x = 0^\pm$ and $x = x_e^\pm$

$\theta(0^-, 0) = \theta(0^+, 0) = 0$ $\theta(x_e^-, 0) = \theta(x_e^+, 0) = \vartheta \gamma \frac{3\sqrt{3}\Gamma(\frac{2}{3})}{2\pi} x_e^{\frac{1}{3}}$	(26a) ₁
$\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(0^-, 0) = \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(0^+, 0) = \vartheta \frac{\sigma^{\frac{1}{3}} \gamma}{\alpha^{\frac{1}{3}}} \left(\frac{3}{4} e^{-\alpha x_e} - \frac{3}{4} \right)$ $\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(x_e^-, 0) = \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(x_e^+, 0) = \vartheta \frac{\sigma^{\frac{1}{3}} \gamma}{\alpha^{\frac{1}{3}}} \left(\frac{3}{4} - \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{t^6 e^{-at^3 x_e}}{t^8 + t^4 + 1} dt \right) - \vartheta \gamma \frac{3\sqrt{3}\Gamma(\frac{2}{3})}{2\pi} x_e^{\frac{1}{3}}$	(26c) ₁
$p(0^-) = p(0^+) = \vartheta \frac{\sigma^{\frac{2}{3}}}{\alpha} \left(\frac{3}{4} - \frac{3}{4} e^{-\alpha x_e} \right)$ $p(x_e^-) = p(x_e^+) = \frac{\vartheta \sigma^{\frac{2}{3}}}{\alpha} \left(\frac{3\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{e^{-at^3 x_e}}{t^8 + t^4 + 1} dt - \frac{3}{4} \right)$	(26d) ₁
$\theta(0^-, 0) = \theta(0^+, 0) = 0$ $\theta(x_e^-, 0) = \theta(x_e^+, 0) = \vartheta \left(1 - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{-\frac{2}{3}} e^{-rx_e}}{r^{\frac{8}{3} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{\frac{4}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}}} dr \right)$	(26a) ₂
$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y}(0^-, 0) = \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y}(0^+, 0) + \vartheta \kappa = 0$ $\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y}(x_e^-, 0) = \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y}(x_e^+, 0) - \vartheta \kappa = -\vartheta \kappa \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{-\frac{2}{3}} e^{-rx_e}}{r^{\frac{8}{3} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{\frac{4}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}}} dr$	(26b) ₂
$\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(0^-, 0) = \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(0^+, 0) = \vartheta \sigma^{\frac{1}{3}} \frac{3}{4} \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}}}{\alpha^{\frac{1}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}}} (e^{-\alpha x_e} - 1)$ $\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(x_e^-, 0) = \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(x_e^+, 0) = \vartheta \sigma^{\frac{1}{3}} \left\{ \frac{3}{4} \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}}}{\alpha^{\frac{1}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}}} + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{(-\beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^2 + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} r^{\frac{1}{3}}) e^{-rx_e}}{(r^{\frac{8}{3}} + r^{\frac{4}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \alpha^{\frac{8}{3}})(r^{\frac{8}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{\frac{4}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}})} dr \right\}$ $- \vartheta \left(1 - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{-\frac{2}{3}} e^{-rx_e}}{r^{\frac{8}{3} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{\frac{4}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}}} dr \right)$	(26c) ₂
$p(0^-) = p(0^+) = \frac{\vartheta \sigma^{\frac{2}{3}}}{\gamma} \frac{3}{4} \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}}}{\alpha^{\frac{1}{3}}(\alpha^{\frac{1}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}})} (1 - e^{-\alpha x_e})$ $p(x_e^-) = p(x_e^+) = \frac{\vartheta \sigma^{\frac{2}{3}}}{\gamma} \left\{ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{(\beta^{\frac{2}{3}} r + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} r^{-\frac{1}{3}}) e^{-rx_e}}{(r^{\frac{8}{3}} + r^{\frac{4}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \alpha^{\frac{8}{3}})(r^{\frac{8}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{\frac{4}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}})} dr - \frac{3}{4} \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}}}{\alpha^{\frac{1}{3}}(\alpha^{\frac{1}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}})} \right\}$	(26d) ₂
$\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(0^-, 0) = \vartheta \sigma^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\frac{3}{4} e^{-\alpha x_e} - \frac{3}{4} \right)$	(26c) ₃

$\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(0^+, 0) = \vartheta \sigma^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\frac{3}{4} e^{-\alpha x_e} + \frac{1}{4} \right) - \vartheta$ $\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(x_e^-, 0) = \vartheta \sigma^{\frac{1}{3}} \left\{ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} r^{\frac{1}{3}} e^{-rx_e}}{r^{\frac{8}{3} + r^{\frac{4}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \alpha^{\frac{8}{3}}} dr + \frac{3}{4} \right\} - \vartheta$ $\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}(x_e^+, 0) = \vartheta \sigma^{\frac{1}{3}} \left\{ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} r^{\frac{1}{3}} e^{-rx_e}}{r^{\frac{8}{3} + r^{\frac{4}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \alpha^{\frac{8}{3}}} dr - \frac{1}{4} \right\}$	
$p(0^-) = p(0^+) = \frac{\vartheta \sigma^{\frac{2}{3}}}{\gamma \alpha^{\frac{3}{4}}} (1 - e^{-\alpha x_e})$ $p(x_e^-) = p(x_e^+) = \frac{\vartheta \sigma^{\frac{2}{3}}}{\gamma \alpha^{\frac{3}{4}}} \left\{ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{(\alpha^{\frac{2}{3}} r + \alpha^{\frac{6}{3}} r^{-\frac{1}{3}}) e^{-rx_e}}{r^{\frac{8}{3} + r^{\frac{4}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \alpha^{\frac{8}{3}}} dr - \frac{3}{4} \right\}$	(26d) ₃

7. Conclusion

Within the frame of the supersonic triple deck theory, the flow past a plate with local thermal disturbance is considered. The linearized form of the lower deck equations, when the disturbance is small, is constructed and manipulated through Fourier transform technique.

Analysis of the linearized problem leads to the following conclusions.

Case 1: Essentially insulated surface with local heat flux.

- The constant heat flux condition is approximated by a condition of constant surface heat transfer rate.
- An extended heat flux is unfeasible, as it leads to thermal blowup.
- The surface temperature, surface shear, and pressure are continuous at both ends of the flux strip.
- Ahead of the flux strip, the free interaction is compressive, causing rise in pressure. Along the strip the pressure drops, causing over expansion. Aft of the strip, the pressure rises again to its undisturbed value.
- The temperature reaches its asymptotic value of zero as $x^{-\frac{2}{3}}$ as $x \sim \infty$.

Cases 2: Dry side of plate has extended or local change in temperature.

- Both extended and local disturbances are feasible.
- The surface temperature, surface shear and pressure are continuous at ends of the disturbance strip, in spite of the discontinuity in the dry surface temperature.
- In case of extended disturbance, the surface temperature T increases monotonically from its value of unity at $x = 0$ to its asymptotic value of $1 + \varepsilon \vartheta$ as $x \sim \infty$.

Cases 3: Wet side of plate has extended or local change in temperature.

- Both extended and local disturbances are feasible.
- The surface shear and pressure are discontinuous at ends of the disturbance strip, due to the discontinuity in the wet surface temperature.

- The surface heat transfer rate behaves as $x^{-\frac{1}{3}}$ as $x \downarrow 0$ and as $(x - x_e)^{-\frac{1}{3}}$ as $x \downarrow x_e$. As $x \sim \infty$, it approaches its asymptotic value of zero as $x^{-\frac{1}{3}}$ in the extended change case, and as $x^{-\frac{4}{3}}$ in the local change case.

In all three cases, the velocity/pressure field exhibits upstream influence, whereas the temperature field does not.

References

- [1] G. R. Inger, Triple-deck theory of supersonic laminar viscous–inviscid interaction due to wall temperature jumps, *Progress in Aerospace Sciences* 43 (2007) 42–63.
 [2] M. V. Koroteev and I. I. Lipatov, Supersonic boundary layer in regions with small temperature perturbations on the wall, *SIAM J. Appl. Math.* 70 (2009) 1139–1156.

Appendix A

Consider the integrals appearing in (23c)₂ and (23d)₂, with $x = 0$,

$I_u = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{-\beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^2 + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} r^{\frac{1}{3}}}{(r^{\frac{8}{3}} + r^{\frac{4}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \alpha^{\frac{8}{3}})(r^{\frac{2}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{\frac{1}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}})} dr$	(A1) _u
$I_p = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\beta^{\frac{2}{3}} r + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} r^{-\frac{1}{3}}}{(r^{\frac{8}{3}} + r^{\frac{4}{3}} \alpha^{\frac{4}{3}} + \alpha^{\frac{8}{3}})(r^{\frac{2}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}} r^{\frac{1}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{2}{3}})} dr$	(A1) _p

They can be expressed, by the substitutions $a = \alpha^{\frac{1}{3}}$, $b = \beta^{\frac{1}{3}}$, $r = z^3$ and the use of partial fractions, as

$I_u = \frac{1}{b^4 - a^4} \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \left[\int_0^\infty \frac{a^4 b z^6 - a^4 b^2 z^5 + a^4 b^4 z^3 - a^8 b^2 z + a^8 b^3}{z^8 + a^4 z^4 + a^8} dz - \int_0^\infty \frac{b^5}{z^2 + b z + b^2} dz \right]$	(A2) _u
$I_p = \frac{1}{b^4 - a^4} \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \left[\int_0^\infty \frac{-b^3 z^6 + b^4 z^5 - a^4 b^2 z^3 + a^4 b^4 z - a^8 b}{z^8 + a^4 z^4 + a^8} dz + \int_0^\infty \frac{b^3}{z^2 + b z + b^2} dz \right]$	(A2) _p

The substitutions $z = at$ in the first integrals and $z = bt$ in the second integrals yield

$I_u = \frac{1}{b^4 - a^4} \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \left[\int_0^\infty \frac{a^3 b t^6 - a^2 b^2 t^5 + b^4 t^3 - a^2 b^2 t + a b^3}{t^8 + t^4 + 1} dt - \int_0^\infty \frac{b^4}{t^2 + t + 1} dt \right]$	(A3) _u
$I_p = \frac{1}{b^4 - a^4} \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{2\pi} \left[\int_0^\infty \frac{-a^{-1} b^3 t^6 + a^{-2} b^4 t^5 - b^2 t^3 + a^{-2} b^4 t - a b}{t^8 + t^4 + 1} dt + \int_0^\infty \frac{b^2}{t^2 + t + 1} dt \right]$	(A3) _p

which evaluate to

$I_u = \frac{1}{b^4 - a^4} \left[\left(\frac{3}{4} a^3 b - \frac{3}{8} a^2 b^2 + \frac{1}{4} b^4 - \frac{3}{8} a^2 b^2 + \frac{3}{4} a b^3 \right) - b^4 \right]$	(A3) _u
$I_p = \frac{1}{b^4 - a^4} \left[\left(-\frac{3}{4} a^{-1} b^3 + \frac{3}{8} a^{-2} b^4 - \frac{1}{4} b^2 + \frac{3}{8} a^{-2} b^4 - \frac{3}{4} a b \right) + b^2 \right]$	(A3) _p

Reverse substitution and manipulation give

$I_u = -\frac{3}{4} \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}}}{\alpha^{\frac{1}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}}}$	(A4) _u
$I_p = \frac{3}{4} \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{3}}}{\alpha^{\frac{2}{3}} (\alpha^{\frac{1}{3}} + \beta^{\frac{1}{3}})}$	(A4) _p